

Full Length Article

Amorphous and dual-phase nanocomposite coatings within the Zr-Cu-B system

Deepika Thakur ^a, Michaela Červená ^a, Jiří Houška ^a, Stanislav Haviar ^a, Tomasz Wojcik ^b, Radomír Čerstvý ^a, Alexander Kirnbauer ^b, Paul Heinz Mayrhofer ^b, Petr Zeman ^{a,*}

^a Department of Physics and NTIS – European Centre of Excellence, University of West Bohemia in Pilsen, Univerzitní 8, 301 00 Pilsen, Czech Republic

^b Institute of Materials Science and Technology, TU Wien, A-1060 Vienna, Austria

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Zr-Cu-B
Zirconium diboride
ZrCu glass
Nanocomposite
Dual-phase structure
Magnetron sputtering

ABSTRACT

Ternary Zr-Cu-B coatings have been prepared using magnetron co-sputtering technique, employing both conventional direct current and high-power impulse magnetron sputtering sources. The study combined detailed experimental structural investigations via X-ray diffraction and electron microscopy with ab-initio simulations of atomic structures for the same compositions of the coatings. A dual-phase nanocomposite structure was identified, consisting of a hard nanocrystalline ZrB₂ phase and a soft amorphous ZrCu phase. By varying the ZrB₂ content (50, 70, and 85 mol.%) while maintaining the same stoichiometry, significant structural evolution was observed. The Zr-Cu-B coatings deposited without heating were amorphous, but simulations revealed composition-dependent segregation tendencies. Increasing substrate temperature promoted phase segregation, leading to the growth of ZrB₂ nanocrystals. The size, orientation, and distribution of these nanocrystals were strongly influenced by the fraction of both phases. At 50 mol.% ZrB₂, the ZrB₂ nanocrystals (1–2 nm) were formed in coatings deposited at a substrate temperature of 450 °C, while higher ZrB₂ fractions enabled segregation at lower temperatures. Mechanical properties, including hardness, reduced Young's modulus, and plasticity, were closely linked to compositional and structural changes. Compared to binary ZrB₂ coatings, the Zr-Cu-B coatings exhibited enhanced plasticity and superior resistance to cracking, highlighting their potential for advanced applications.

1. Introduction

In the last decades, transition metal (TM) nitrides, carbides, and diborides coatings have gained great interest due to their unique combinations of physical and functional properties, such as high melting point, high hardness, enhanced wear resistance, and excellent thermal stability. These characteristics make them highly suitable in the field of protective coatings, aerospace and engine components, cutting tools, or wear-resistant surfaces [1–6]. Their properties can be tailored by carefully selecting appropriate constituent elements and optimizing the process parameters of the deposition technique. However, their practical application is often limited by their intrinsic brittleness, which makes them susceptible to cracking or failure under strain.

To overcome this limitation, combining these hard ceramic phases with soft metallic constituents has proven to be an effective strategy for enhancing toughness and enabling plastic deformation [7]. Attention has been paid to dual-phase nanocomposite coatings primarily

composed of a TM nitride and a single-element metal (e.g., Cu, Ni, Ag) [8–15]. An example is Zr-Cu-N coatings composed of ZrN and Cu phases, which exhibit enhanced plastic deformation behaviour and simultaneously antibacterial performance [14,15]. Their synthesis relies on maintaining a sufficiently high N₂ partial pressure in the deposition chamber, ensuring that all sputtered Zr atoms react with nitrogen, while Cu does not due to the positive mixing enthalpy. Recently, we have also shown for the first time [16] that this ternary system can serve as the basis for forming dual-phase nanocomposite coatings composed of ZrN and ZrCu metallic glass. In this case, the N₂ partial pressure must be low enough to allow only part of Zr atoms to react with nitrogen, while the remaining Zr atoms mix with Cu to form an amorphous ZrCu phase. By optimizing the fractions of these two phases, an enhancement in hardness and a control of deformation behaviour can be achieved.

Among the TM ceramic coatings, TM diborides offer several advantages over their nitride and carbide counterparts, primarily due to their unique bonding structure, which results in superior hardness, thermal

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: zemanp@kfy.zcu.cz (P. Zeman).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apsusc.2025.165766>

Received 5 November 2025; Received in revised form 18 December 2025; Accepted 29 December 2025

Available online 30 December 2025

0169-4332/© 2026 The Authors. Published by Elsevier B.V. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

stability, oxidation resistance, and electrical/thermal conductivity [17–19]. TM diborides possess an AlB_2 type hexagonal structure with a distinctive ceramic/metallic nature, characterized by the ionic-covalent bonding between metal and B atoms, strong covalent bonding within graphite-like honeycomb B sheets, and metallic/covalent bonding in the metal Zr layers [20,21].

Similar to TM nitrides and carbides, overcoming the inherent brittleness of TM diborides remains a major challenge. Surprisingly, however, studies exploring their combination with soft metallic phases in the nanocomposite structure are relatively scarce in the literature and often focus on properties other than mechanical ones. For example, Wu et al. [22] co-sputtered ZrB_2 and Cu targets, but their interest was in increasing electron concentration in the coatings to achieve sufficiently low infrared emissivity and high infrared reflectivity. Similarly, Zhang et al. [23] prepared Ag- ZrB_2 composite coatings with low infrared emissivity, low visible light reflectance, and hydrophobicity. Notably, only the study by Fiantok et al. [24] focused on the mechanical properties of ZrB_2 -Ag nanocomposite coatings over a wide compositional range. They found that the addition of Ag reduced hardness and Young's modulus but improved toughness, ductile behavior, and tribological performance. Other studies investigating the addition of TMs to TM diborides have predominantly resulted in the formation of alloyed single-phase TM diboride coatings rather than true nanocomposite structures [6,25,26].

In the present work, we build upon the concept demonstrated for Zr-Cu-N coatings composed of ZrN and ZrCu phases [16] and, for the first time, explore the possibility of forming a dual-phase nanocomposite structure consisting of nanocrystalline ZrB_2 and amorphous ZrCu within the Zr-Cu-B system. The synthesis strategy is based on the negative mixing enthalpy of Zr with B and Cu, as opposed to the positive mixing enthalpy of Cu with B. Our focus is specifically on such elemental compositions where the stoichiometry of the two phases remains the same and only the molar phase fraction varies. This study represents an early step in a broader research program aimed at developing thin-film materials with dual-phase structures. Here, we pay particular attention to a systematic and detailed investigation of the structural evolution as a function of the molar phase fraction and the substrate temperature during deposition. To complement the experimental findings, *ab initio* simulations were performed to gain deeper insights into the segregation tendencies and bonding characteristics within the system.

2. Methodology

2.1. Experimental methods

The Zr-Cu-B coatings were deposited using an AJA International ATC 2200-V deposition system, comprising four unbalanced magnetrons, three direct current (DC) sputtering units, and one high-power impulse magnetron sputtering unit (HiPIMS). The magnetrons were equipped with two dense ZrB_2 (99.5 %, Zr:B stoichiometric ratio 1:2) compound targets, a metallic Zr (99.5 %) target, and a metallic Cu (99.99 %) target. Each target had a diameter of 50.8 mm and a thickness of 6 mm and was positioned at a fixed tilt angle at a distance of 150 mm from a rotating substrate holder operating at 40 rpm. Prior to deposition, Si(100) substrates were ultrasonically cleaned in isopropyl for 10 min and were etched in an Ar atmosphere for 300 s by radio frequency (RF) discharge at a power of 30 W. The deposition chamber was evacuated to a base pressure below 5.0×10^{-5} Pa, using a turbomolecular pump with a pumping speed of 1200 l/s backed up by a multi-stage roots pump with a capacity of 27 m³/hr. The coatings were sputtered in pure Ar, keeping the total working pressure at 0.533 Pa (4 mTorr) inside the chamber.

The ZrB_2 targets and the Zr target were powered by two separate DC power supplies (Advanced Energy Pinnacle Plus + 5/5 kW and AJA International DCXS-750-4), while the Cu target was driven by a pulsed DC power supply (Hüttinger Elektronik TruPlasma Highpulse 4002) operated in HiPIMS mode. During deposition, the average power density

applied to the Cu target during each pulse was maintained at 1000 W/cm². The duration of the negative voltage pulse was set to a constant value of 200 μ s.

To achieve the desired coating compositions, the deposition rates from the individual targets were calibrated prior to each deposition using a quartz crystal deposition rate monitor (Inficon SQM-160). These rates were controlled by adjusting the DC powers for the Zr (20–210 W) and ZrB_2 (130–150 W) targets and the average target power in a period for the Cu HiPIMS through regulation of the repetition frequency (5–23 Hz). To enhance the energy of incoming ions and produce densified coatings, the substrates were subjected to a constant RF bias (30 W) throughout all depositions. Furthermore, the depositions were carried out both without the substrate heating and at elevated temperatures of 250 °C, 350 °C, and 450 °C.

The elemental composition of the coatings was analyzed using wavelength dispersive spectroscopy (WDS, Thermo Scientific MagnaRay) integrated into a scanning electron microscope (SEM, Hitachi SU-70). The SEM was operated at a primary electron energy of 10 keV, and bulk standards were used for quantification of all elements. The measurement error can be estimated to be 2 at.%. Cross-sectional micrographs of the simply fractured coatings were acquired using the same SEM, operated at a reduced primary electron energy of 5 keV.

X-ray diffraction (XRD) was performed on the coatings deposited on Si substrates to characterize their structure. The measurements were conducted using a diffractometer (PANalytical X'Pert PRO) with Cu $K\alpha$ radiation ($\lambda = 0.154187$ nm). The instrument was operated in Bragg-Brentano geometry with an ω -offset of 1.5° to suppress the strong reflection from the Si(100) substrate. Data were collected over a 2θ range of 20° to 100° and analyzed using the PANalytical HighScore Plus software package.

The detailed examination of microstructure was performed for some selected coatings deposited on silicon substrates by transmission electron microscopy (TEM, FEI TECNAI F20). TEM was operated at 200 kV in bright field and high-angle annular dark-field scanning TEM (BF, HAADF, STEM) mode for imaging, selected area electron diffraction (SAED), and high-resolution TEM (HRTEM) imaging. Thin cross-sectional lamellae for TEM were fabricated using a standard lift-out procedure with a ThermoFisher Scios 2 focused ion beam (FIB) system.

The hardness, reduced Young's modulus, and plasticity work fraction of the coatings were evaluated by using a nanoindentation tester (Hysitron TI950 TriboIndenter) equipped with a Berkovich-type diamond tip under a load of 10 mN. To minimize the effects of the substrate, the indentation depth was kept below 10 % of the coating thickness. Sixteen indentations were performed on two different positions for each sample, and an average value was evaluated. To understand the plastic behavior of the coatings, the nanoindentation tests were also performed by UMIS CSIRO nanoindenter equipped with a cube-corner indenter on Si substrate applying loads ranging from 50 mN to 450 mN. The coating thickness and residual stress values based on modified Stoney's equation were measured by the surface profilometer (Veeco Dektak 8 Stylus) on the Si substrates.

The coating topography and arithmetic surface roughness were examined by atomic force microscopy (AIST-NT SmartSPM) equipped with a silicon tip with a nominal radius of 10 nm. The measurements were performed under semi-contact tapping mode, and an area of $5 \times 5 \mu\text{m}^2$ was scanned.

2.2. Computational method

All *ab-initio* simulations of Zr-Cu-B materials were performed using the density functional theory as implemented in the CPMD code [27], in a 64-atom periodic cell (see below for the compositions and densities). The atom cores and inner electron shells were represented by Goedecker type pseudopotentials. The wavefunction of valence electrons was expanded in a plane wave basis set with an energy cutoff of 50 Ry and (owing to the amorphous nature and size of the simulation cell) no k-

points except the gamma point.

The simulations utilized the liquid-quench algorithm [28], which captures the conditions arising after an energetic ion impact. This impact melts down a small volume of the material and generates thermal spikes. The individual parts of the algorithm included (i) mixing of atoms at 6000 K (safely above the melting temperature, i.e. at no stable bond formation) for 2 ps, (ii) exponential cooling down to a representative preparation temperature of 450 K for 2 ps, (iii) equilibration at 450 K for 2 ps and (iv) collecting structural snapshots at 450 K for 0.5 ps. See [16,29,30] for a previous successful usage of the same algorithm, including a justification of the time scale (for a system where Zr is also the heaviest element).

The bonding statistics were analyzed using bonding distance cutoffs corresponding to upper bounds of first peaks of partial correlation functions (4.000, 3.475, 3.175, 2.975, 2.600, and 2.250 Å for Zr-Zr, Zr-Cu, Zr-B, Cu-Cu, Cu-B, and B-B, respectively). Bonding statistics of amorphous binary B-free ZrCu (Zr₃₂Cu₃₂ simulation cell) were calculated for comparative purposes (Sec. 3.2) using the same simulation technique.

3. Results and discussion

In this section, we present and discuss original results of a detailed and systematic study of the structure evolution of Zr-Cu-B coatings, which were specifically designed to investigate the possibility of the formation of a dual-phase nanocomposite structure consisting of two binary phases, nanocrystalline ZrB₂ and amorphous ZrCu. These results, which represent the core of this study, are further complemented by the initial measurements of the properties of this novel class of coatings.

3.1. Composition

The Zr-Cu-B coatings, approximately 2 μm thick, were prepared with three different compositions at varying substrate temperatures. The elemental composition of the coatings was carefully tuned to match the stoichiometric ratios of ZrB₂ (1:2) and ZrCu (1:1) in the coatings. As a result, each of the three series of coatings maintains approximately the same composition, and the series differ from each other only in the molar or volume fraction of the two phases. For comparison, a reference series of binary coatings, which were sputtered only from the ZrB₂ targets under identical deposition conditions, was also included in the study.

Table 1 summarizes the nominal elemental compositions and corresponding molar fractions for all four series. The deposited elemental compositions for all coatings are depicted in the ternary diagram in Fig. 1 and are very close to the nominal values.

As seen, the lowest molar fraction of ZrB₂ in the Zr-Cu-B coatings investigated is 50 %, as coatings with higher ZrCu molar fractions were found to be amorphous, even at the highest achievable substrate temperature (not shown here). This indicates a limited potential for such compositions to form a dual-phase nanocomposite structure. The other two series of the coatings are characterized by 70 and 85 mol.% ZrB₂, respectively. Furthermore, it can be observed that the binary ZrB₂ coatings without Cu are slightly substoichiometric in B, with Zr:B ratios ranging from 0.56 to 0.63. This deviation is likely caused by the preferential resputtering of B atoms due to ion bombardment during

Table 1
Nominal elemental compositions of Zr-Cu-B coatings with corresponding molar fractions of ZrB₂ and ZrCu phases.

Series	Zr (at.%)	Cu (at.%)	B (at.%)	ZrCu (mol.%)	ZrB ₂ (mol.%)
1	40	20	40	50	50
2	37	11	52	30	70
3	35	5	60	14	85
4	34	0	66	0	100

deposition, which is a phenomenon frequently reported in the literature [31,32].

3.2. Structure deposited without heating

Similar to our previous work on the Zr-Cu-N coatings [16], we first deposited Zr-Cu-B coatings without external substrate heating. Fig. 2 presents their XRD patterns for all investigated compositions, alongside those of a binary ZrB₂ coating deposited under identical conditions and a binary ZrCu coating from the Zr-Cu-N series.

The XRD patterns of the Zr-Cu-B coatings reveal a broad scattering peak (hump), characteristic of the amorphous nature of materials, in contrast to the ZrB₂ coatings, which exhibit sharp diffraction peaks corresponding to the hexagonal ZrB₂ phase (PDF Card No. 00-034-0423). Compared to the ZrCu coating, which has been identified as a metallic glass with medium-range ordering of atoms preferentially in icosahedral clusters [33,34], the humps of the Zr-Cu-B coatings shift gradually to lower diffraction angles and become broader as the B content increases. This indicates structural changes, such as increased spacing between Zr and Cu atoms and enhanced disorder, caused by the incorporation of smaller B atoms. These B atoms disrupt the local atomic arrangement of Zr and Cu, creating a more open and disordered structure.

In addition, light boron with a lower number of electrons reduces the probability of X-ray scattering, contributing to the reduced intensity of the amorphous hump. For coatings with 70 and 85 mol.% ZrB₂, an asymmetry in the hump shape can also be observed. This asymmetry likely arises from compositional inhomogeneity on the atomic scale, where some regions are enriched in certain elements while others are deficient, leading to variations in local atomic arrangements.

Fig. 3 shows the morphology of the coatings in cross-sectional SEM micrographs. As expected, all Zr-Cu-B coatings exhibit a featureless, amorphous-like microstructure, consistent with their XRD patterns characterized by amorphous humps. This is the effect of amorphization of the coatings rather than their densification induced by sputtering of Cu using HiPIMS. In contrast, the ZrB₂ coating, which exhibits sharp diffraction peaks, grows with a columnar microstructure typical of crystalline sputter-deposited coatings. The columns are relatively narrow and closely attached, with no significant voids, indicating growth behavior characteristic of the transition between zone I and zone T, as described by structure zone models [35,36].

To verify the completely amorphous structure or identify the presence of extremely small nanocrystals in the Zr-Cu-B coatings, we selected the coating with the theoretically highest ZrB₂ fraction (85 mol. %) for detailed TEM analysis in a cross-section. This investigation included SAED, BF and HRTEM imaging, with the results presented in Fig. 4. The BF micrograph is characterized by a uniform, homogenous microstructure without any visible grains and boundaries. The corresponding SAED pattern displays a diffuse halo, an indication of a random arrangement of atoms, and the lack of periodic atomic structure. The HRTEM micrograph further confirms the amorphous nature, with no evidence of crystalline regions. However, small regions with a darker contrast, approximately 1–2 nm in size, are visible. These features may be attributed to chemical inhomogeneities, incipient phase separation, or density fluctuations within the amorphous matrix.

3.3. Simulated atomic structure

To gain deeper insight into the atomic structure and bonding of the Zr-Cu-B coatings, four *ab initio* simulations were conducted using a 64-atom simulation cell. Three of these simulations (Zr₂₆Cu₁₃B₂₅, Zr₂₄Cu₇B₃₃, and Zr₂₂Cu₃B₃₉) correspond to the same ternary compositions studied experimentally, with slight adjustments to ensure integer numbers of atoms for each element and an even number of valence electrons. The fourth simulation (Zr₂₈Cu₁₈B₁₈) was included to extend the compositional range by exploring also coatings with a lower ZrB₂

Fig. 1. Ternary diagram on the left shows the elemental compositions of deposited Zr-Cu-B coatings, while a schematic on the right illustrates the change of molar fractions of ZrCu and ZrB₂ phases at different deposition temperatures. The colors of the square symbols in the ternary diagram correspond to the deposition temperatures indicated in the schematic.

Fig. 2. XRD patterns of Zr-Cu-B coatings with different ZrB₂ molar fractions deposited without substrate heating. The diffraction peak observed in all patterns at approximately 69° corresponds to the Si(100) substrate.

fraction.

The results presented graphically are valid for the simulation cell density equal to 100 % of the weighted average densities of the corresponding crystalline phases, consistent with the approach used in Section 3.1 to calculate molar fractions of the coatings. Lower density factors of 90 % and 80 % were also considered, the results did not provide any new information beyond the formation of pores, which were not observed experimentally. This suggests that the 100 % density assumption aligns more closely with experimental conditions.

The snapshots of the atomic structures of the Zr-Cu-B coatings are presented in Fig. 5, providing a visual representation of their simulated atomic arrangements. The corresponding bonding statistics are summarized in Fig. 6a, allowing for a detailed analysis of the types and distribution of chemical bonds. For comparison, the bonding statistics of as-deposited Zr-Cu-N coatings from a previous study [16] are also included in Fig. 6c. The bottom panels (Fig. 6b and Fig. 6d) provide additional information on the bonding statistics, which would have the

Fig. 3. Cross-sectional SEM micrographs of Zr-Cu-B coatings with different ZrB₂ molar fractions deposited without substrate heating.

ideally segregated systems, ZrB₂ + ZrCu and ZrN + ZrCu, respectively.

As shown in Fig. 5, the atomic structures of the Zr-Cu-B coatings obtained at the end of a thermal spike (but without any diffusion at the deposition temperature and a long time scale) appear visually amorphous. This observation is different from the Zr-Cu-N coatings, which tend to strictly follow the bonding trends of an ideally segregated system. However, if the Zr-Cu-B coatings were not only amorphous but fully homogeneous, then the bonding statistics in Fig. 6a would be completely different. Instead, there are fingerprints of segregation that depend on the composition of coatings, as discussed further below. That is, the bonding statistics of the actual structure of the Zr-Cu-B coatings follow similar trends to those of the Zr-Cu-N coatings, but deviate quantitatively from the ideal segregated case (Fig. 6b), especially at a lower molar fraction of ZrB₂. This suggests that the Zr-Cu-B system exhibits a higher resistance towards segregation compared to the Zr-Cu-N system under deposition conditions without any external heating. This finding is consistent with the structural analysis described in Sec. 3.2.

Analyzing the data in more detail, aside from the predictable trends (i.e., the replacement of ZrCu by ZrB₂ decreases the number of Zr-Cu and Cu-Cu bonds while increasing the number of Zr-B and B-B bonds), reveals several important insights in the bonding statistics presented in

Fig. 4. Cross-sectional BF micrograph with an inset of SAED pattern (on the top) and cross-sectional HRTEM micrograph (at the bottom) of a Zr-Cu-B coating with 85 mol.% ZrB₂ deposited without substrate heating.

Fig. 6a. First, the number of Zr-Zr bonds decreases because Zr constitutes half of ZrCu but only third of ZrB₂, while the number of Cu-B bonds decreases within the present B-rich compositional range (considering the entire range from ZrCu to ZrB₂ would show a concave dependence). Second, there are fingerprints of segregation into ZrCu and ZrB₂ phases, even within the limited time scale of simulations. This is evident from bond ratios: the [Zr-B]/[Cu-B] bond number ratio is consistently higher ($1.03 \times$ to $1.51 \times$) than the corresponding [Zr atoms \times Zr coordination]/[Cu atoms \times Cu coordination] ratio, and the [Zr-Cu]/[Cu-B] bond number ratio is higher ($1.03 \times$ to $1.65 \times$) than the corresponding [Zr atoms \times Zr coordination]/[B atoms \times B coordination] ratio. Visual evidence of segregation is also apparent in Fig. 5, where B-free and Cu-free zones can be seen. Third, comparing the actual bonding statistics of Zr-Cu-B (Fig. 6a) with those of the idealized segregated ZrCu + ZrB₂ (Fig. 6b; at no Cu-B bonds by definition) shows the most important difference in the number of B-B bonds. At relatively lower B contents, the actual number of B-B bonds is much lower than expected after the segregation, while at the higher B contents, it approaches the expected values. In parallel, the actual and expected numbers of Zr-Zr and Zr-B bonds are comparable across all compositions. Thus, a case can be made that the bottleneck, which controls the composition-dependent segregation and subsequent crystallization (easier at higher B contents), is the formation of B-B bonds.

3.4. Structure deposited at elevated temperature

To facilitate the segregation process and promote the formation of a dual-phase nanocomposite structure consisting of the nanocrystalline ZrB₂ and amorphous ZrCu phases, we deposited all the investigated compositions at elevated temperatures of 250 °C, 350 °C, and 450 °C. Fig. 7 illustrates the structure evolution represented by XRD patterns for all these temperatures, while Fig. 8 presents cross-sectional BF micrographs with SAED insets and HRTEM micrographs for the highest temperature of 450 °C.

The XRD patterns (Fig. 7) reveal that an increase in deposition temperature positively influences segregation by enhancing the diffusion processes of deposited atoms on the surface and within the Zr-Cu-B coatings. In parallel, as the B content increases, which is accompanied by a reduction in the amount of the amorphous ZrCu phase, the segregation process becomes more favorable even at lower temperatures.

At 50 mol.% ZrB₂ (Fig. 7a), the XRD patterns of the coatings are similar up to 350 °C, i.e., characterized by a broad amorphous hump. The only noticeable difference is a shift in the maximum of the hump (by $\sim 0.5^\circ$) to the position corresponding to the binary ZrCu coating (Fig. 2) as the deposition temperature increases from 250 °C to 350 °C. This shift may suggest the phase separation of the homogeneous amorphous structure to B-rich and Cu-rich amorphous domains. At the highest deposition temperature of 450 °C, a more pronounced change in the shape of the hump occurs, indicating an onset of nucleation of tiny (not necessarily stoichiometric) ZrB₂ crystallites. This observation is further corroborated by a SAED pattern (inset in Fig. 8a). In addition to the amorphous halo in the SAED pattern, two faint diffraction spots are visible, corresponding to the (10 $\bar{1}$ 0) plane of the hcp ZrB₂ lattice. These spots indicate a texture parallel to the surface, which is consistent with the orientation observed in the XRD pattern. A HRTEM micrograph (Fig. 8a) provides additional evidence, revealing the presence of tiny nanocrystallites (marked by yellow), only a few atomic layers in size (approximately 1–2 nm), embedded within the predominantly amorphous matrix. The overall microstructure of this coating appears homogeneous and amorphous-like, with no indication of columnar growth, as confirmed by a BF micrograph in Fig. 8a.

At 70 mol.% ZrB₂ (Fig. 7b), the first signs of nucleation of very small ZrB₂ nanocrystallites are observed in the XRD pattern of the coating prepared at 350 °C, while the coating grown at 450 °C already contains well-developed ZrB₂ nanocrystals with a strongly preferred (0001) orientation. The textured growth, with the *c*-axis of the hcp lattice oriented perpendicular to the coating surface, is also proved by a SAED pattern shown in the inset of Fig. 8b. A HRTEM micrograph (Fig. 8b) reveals ZrB₂ nanocrystals (highlighted by yellow) ranging in size from 2 to 7 nm, with the preferred orientation detected by SAED. These include (0001) planes parallel to the surface, (10 $\bar{1}$ 0) planes perpendicular to the surface, and (10 $\bar{1}$ 1) planes properly inclined to the surface. The nanocrystals are surrounded by an amorphous matrix. Furthermore, a BF micrograph in Fig. 8b shows that the coating grows with a fine-grained columnar microstructure at this composition.

At 85 mol.% ZrB₂ (Fig. 7c), ZrB₂ diffraction peaks starts to emerge already at a lower deposition temperature of 250 °C. The (0001) peak appears narrower and is accompanied by broader peaks representing smaller ZrB₂ nanocrystals of other orientations. Notably, the (0001) peak seems to be a superposition of two peaks of different widths but the same orientation. As the deposition temperature increases, the intensities of all peaks rise, and their widths narrow, indicating the growth of ZrB₂ nanocrystals. The presence of more randomly oriented ZrB₂ nanocrystals at this composition is confirmed by relatively continuous diffraction rings in the SAED pattern (inset in Fig. 8c). The (0001) orientation, however, exhibits a slight texture, as evidenced by a less continuous ring. HRTEM and BF micrographs (Fig. 8c) provide additional evidence that the coating is predominantly crystalline, with a columnar microstructure composed of ZrB₂ nanocrystals of different

Fig. 5. Snapshots of the atomic structures of Zr-Cu-B simulation cells. Columns correspond to the respective compositions and rows represent simulation cell density equal to (a) 100%, (b) 90% and (c) 80% of the weighted average of densities of corresponding crystalline phases.

orientations. An elevated background in the XRD patterns and disordered areas at columnar boundaries (brighter contrast in the HRTEM image) confirms that the amorphous phase is also present in these coatings.

The findings presented above can be explained by a combination of thermodynamics (increasingly straightforward with decreasing Cu content) governing the short-time-scale nucleation of ZrB₂ at the surface of the growing coatings with the kinetics of the long-time-scale nucleation of ZrB₂ in the coating volume that is effectively annealed at the deposition temperature. As calculated in [37], for Zr-rich conditions and Zr-terminated surfaces (arguably the most relevant case for the present elemental compositions), the surface energy of ZrB₂ (0001) of 1.81 J/m² is lower than that of other ZrB₂ orientations of 1.88–3.47 J/m². On the one hand, these surface energies explain the preferential surface nucleation of ZrB₂ (0001) and determine the important role of this orientation in the coatings. On the other hand, the volume nucleation of ZrB₂ well below the surface is, of course, independent of surface energies and leads to random orientations of the resulting nanocrystals.

Collectively, these phenomena resulted in the following. At 50 mol.% ZrB₂ (Fig. 7a), the present range of the deposition temperature does not allow for any convincing surface nucleation and subsequent growth of ZrB₂ (0001) (although the change in the shape of the broad diffraction halo at the highest temperature of 450 °C indicates an onset of nucleation of tiny crystallites of a different orientation, arguably controlled by orientation-dependent surface diffusion rate of Cu and/or by different surface energies resulting from the presence of remaining Cu impurities). At 70 mol.% ZrB₂ (Fig. 7b), the highest temperature of 450 °C allows for surface nucleation of ZrB₂ (0001) nanocrystals, but not yet volume nucleation of ZrB₂ in the remaining amorphous phase, which contains a lower molar fraction of ZrB₂ (there is actually a similar case demonstrated in Fig. 7a for one such lower fraction). Thus, the

subsequent growth of ZrB₂ (0001) nanocrystals (resulting from uncorrelated diffusion of individual atoms, i.e., kinetically easier than the nucleation) is not spatially limited by anything else than other ZrB₂ (0001) nanocrystals, leading to the dominance of this XRD reflection.

Further enhancement of the ZrB₂ fraction to 86 mol.% (Fig. 7c) promotes volume nucleation of additional nanocrystals of various orientations (including (0001)). Their subsequent growth is then spatially limited by one another. This leads to (i) smaller sizes of all other nanocrystals than ZrB₂ (0001) existing since their surface nucleation (as evidenced by broader peaks in Fig. 7c), and, paradoxically, even (ii) seemingly smaller sizes of ZrB₂ (0001) nanocrystals at higher molar fractions of ZrB₂ (compare Fig. 7c with Fig. 7b for 450 °C). The larger ZrB₂ fraction also shifts the onset of all nucleation processes to lower temperatures (≤ 250 °C), although the deposition temperature still facilitates these processes (compare individual panels of Fig. 7c). The volume nucleation is of course relevant only when there are any temporarily amorphous zones in the coating volume, which is consistent with the fact that in pure ZrB₂ coatings (Fig. 7d), the (0001) orientation once again becomes dominant.

3.5. Surface topography

The surface topography of Zr-Cu-B coatings, as measured by AFM, correlates well with their structure. Fig. 9 presents representative AFM images of coatings with 85 mol.% ZrB₂ deposited at various temperatures. The coating deposited without heating, characterized by an amorphous structure and a featureless cross-sectional microstructure, exhibits an exceptionally smooth surface with an areal average roughness of only 0.2 nm. Note that this type of smooth surface is also observed in coatings with 50 and 70 mol.% ZrB₂, even though some of these coatings exhibit a dual-phase nanocomposite structure

Fig. 6. Compositional dependences of bonding statistics for Zr-Cu-B (a-b) and Zr-Cu-N (c-d) materials. The top panels (a and c) show results for the actual simulated structures, while the bottom panels (b and d) correspond to ideally segregated systems: $\text{ZrB}_2 + \text{ZrCu}$ (b) and $\text{ZrN} + \text{ZrCu}$ (d). The number of bonds is related to 64 atoms.

(specifically those deposited at 450 °C).

With increasing deposition temperature, the columnar growth of coatings with 85 mol.% ZrB_2 occurs, along with segregation into the dual-phase structure. As a result, the surface roughness gradually increases, and sharp and narrow features evolve on the surface, representing terminations of individual columns. Nevertheless, the highest roughness of 5.0 nm for the coating deposited at 450 °C is still nearly half the values measured for binary ZrB_2 coatings. This suggests that the addition of ZrCu to the ZrB_2 phase promotes grain refinement, resulting in smoother surfaces.

3.6. Mechanical properties

The primary focus of this study is the synthesis and structural characterization of Zr-Cu-B coatings. However, we consider it worthwhile to briefly present and discuss preliminary results on their mechanical properties. A more detailed investigation of these properties, along with their deformation behavior, is planned for future work, once the deposition conditions are further optimized.

Fig. 10 summarizes the measured values of the hardness (H), reduced Young's modulus (E_{IT}), plastic work fraction (W_{pl}/W_t ; the ratio of plastic to total indentation work), and residual stress (σ) for the Zr-Cu-B coatings deposited with varying ZrB_2 molar fractions and at different temperatures. As the ZrB_2 fraction increases in the coatings, both H and E_{IT} exhibit increasing trends (Figs. 10a and 10b), which can be attributed to introducing more covalent bonding to the material with increasing B content. Notably, the values for binary ZrB_2 coatings align with these trends only when deposited without heating. Otherwise, discrepancies in these evolutions are observed for 100 mol.% ZrB_2 .

The values of W_{pl}/W_t naturally follow an opposite trend (Fig. 10c) compared to H (Fig. 10a) and, more prominently, to the H^3/E_{IT}^2 ratio (not shown here), which is widely interpreted as a measure of resistance to plastic deformation [38]. This inverse relationship is illustrated in

Fig. 11, where the H^3/E_{IT}^2 ratio is plotted against W_{pl}/W_t . The data reveal a distinct hyperbolic inverse dependence, with H^3/E_{IT}^2 decreasing as W_{pl}/W_t increases. This behavior highlights that the Zr-Cu-B coatings with lower H^3/E_{IT}^2 values exhibit tendency to deform plastically, as reflected in a higher fraction of plastic work during indentation. Conversely, the coatings with higher H^3/E_{IT}^2 values demonstrate improved resistance to plastic deformation, leading to enhanced elastic recovery and reduced plasticity. Such a relationship aligns with the theoretical framework of material deformation, where hardness and elastic modulus (reflected in the H^3/E_{IT}^2 ratio) synergistically contribute to a material's ability to resist permanent deformation.

With increasing deposition temperature, H and E_{IT} show an increasing trend for the three compositions of the Zr-Cu-B coatings, see Fig. 10a and b. At 50 mol.% ZrB_2 , this increase is the least pronounced compared to other compositions, consistently with the fact that at this composition, the structure remains qualitatively the same (the temperature does not induce crystallinity). The H values range between 9.5 and 11.9 GPa, and E_{IT} between 135 and 161 GPa. Let us note that the lowest value of H is approximately 1.5 times higher than H reported for binary ZrCu coatings [33,39].

As the ZrB_2 fraction increases, the effect of deposition temperature on the mechanical properties becomes more significant. At 70 mol.% ZrB_2 , H increases from 11.9 to 20.0 GPa, and E_{IT} increases from 150 to 206 GPa. Similarly, at 85 mol.% ZrB_2 , H increases from 15.8 to 21.8 GPa, and E_{IT} rises from 179 to 254 GPa. These increases can be attributed to the structural changes occurring in the coatings, as discussed in Sec. 3.4. The segregation of the amorphous structure into a dual-phase nanocomposite structure with increasing deposition temperature can result in two effects. First, ZrB_2 nanocrystals contribute to enhanced mechanical properties through stronger and more uniform covalent bonding and higher density (high bond strength not only per bond but even more importantly per unit volume). Second, they also act as obstacles to the motion and propagation of shear bands, which are characteristic of

Fig. 7. XRD patterns of Zr-Cu-B coatings deposited at various substrate temperatures with (a) 50 mol.% ZrB₂, (b) 70 mol.% ZrB₂, (c) 85 mol.% ZrB₂, and (d) 100 mol.% ZrB₂. The diffraction peak observed in all XRD patterns at approximately 69° corresponds to the Si(100) substrate, with additional Si peaks marked in (a).

plastic deformation in metallic glasses. If the size of nanocrystals is optimized to be separated by a thin amorphous phase, as demonstrated in our previous study on dual-phase nanocomposite Zr-Cu-N coatings [16], significant enhancement of hardness can be achieved due to the synergistic effect of both phases, exceeding the predictions of the rule of mixtures. For the few compositions investigated in this study, it is, however, difficult to clearly reveal this effect in the Zr-Cu-B coatings. Nevertheless, a possible indication is the concave hardness dependence observed for nanocomposites at 450 °C, in contrast to the convex dependencies seen at lower deposition temperatures. The HRTEM micrograph (Fig. 8b) reveals a structure in the Zr-Cu-B coating with 70 mol.% ZrB₂ prepared at 450 °C that closely resembles the structure of the Zr-Cu-N coating with 56 mol.% ZrN, for which a significant hardness enhancement has previously been achieved [16].

For the binary ZrB₂ coatings, on the one hand, measured H and E_{IT} do not increase monotonically with increasing deposition temperature as for the Zr-Cu-B coatings. This is once again consistent with the limited qualitative changes in the coating structure, well crystalline at all deposition temperatures. On the other hand, the discrepancy in H and E_{IT} can be explained by the elemental composition of the ZrB₂ coatings. All coatings exhibit a slight substoichiometry in B content, and this substoichiometry correlates well with the values of H and E_{IT} . The

highest values are observed for the coatings with the highest B content, in the first place, those prepared without heating and at 450 °C. Interestingly, while the highest H values exceed those of the Zr-Cu-B coatings, all E_{IT} values are lower than those of the Zr-Cu-B coatings.

The evolution of σ with the ZrB₂ fraction and the deposition temperature is shown in Fig. 10d. As seen, compressive stress is generated in the coatings deposited without heating or at a low temperature of 250 °C. At higher deposition temperatures, only the coatings with 70 mol.% ZrB₂ retains compressive stress, while all other compositions are in the tensile state. The transition to the tensile stress aligns with the fact that higher deposition temperatures generate larger tensile thermal stresses in the coatings due to larger thermal expansion coefficients of the coatings than the Si(100) substrate.

In many other materials, σ plays an important role in determining H . Compressive stress commonly enhances hardness, while tensile stress is detrimental in this respect. However, comparing Fig. 10a and d reveals that σ has only a minor effect on H for all deposited coatings and more importantly, the composition and structure of the coatings are decisive factors. Indeed, the highest H values are achieved for the highest tensile stress.

To investigate the response of the Zr-Cu-B coatings to larger deformation, indentation experiments were conducted using a cube-corner

Fig. 8. TEM results of Zr-Cu-B coatings prepared at a deposition temperature of 450 °C with varying ZrB₂ molar fractions of (a) 50 mol.%, (b) 70 mol.%, and (c) 85 mol.%. The top row shows cross-sectional BF micrographs with insets of SAED patterns, while the bottom row presents cross-sectional HRTEM micrographs. The lattice planes identified in the SAED patterns correspond to the ZrB₂ phase.

Fig. 9. AFM surface topography images of Zr-Cu-B coatings with 85 mol.% ZrB₂, prepared at different deposition temperatures. The values of the areal average surface roughness are indicated in the top-right corners of each image.

Fig. 10. Compositional dependences of (a) hardness, H , (b) reduced Young's modulus, E_{IT} , (c) plastic work fraction, W_{pl}/W_t , and (d) residual stress, σ , of Zr-Cu-B coatings prepared at different deposition temperatures. The hollow symbols represent the coatings with a dual-phase nanocomposite structure.

Fig. 11. Correlation between the H^3/E_{IT}^2 ratio and plastic work fraction, W_{pl}/W_t , for Zr-Cu-B coatings prepared with different compositions and at different deposition temperatures. The hollow symbols represent the coatings with a dual-phase nanocomposite structure.

indenter. Fig. 12 presents representative indents obtained at a load of 150 mN for all compositions prepared without heating and at the highest temperature of 450 °C.

The results revealed that amorphous Zr-Cu-B coatings deposited without heating demonstrate the highest resistance to cracking among all the coatings. It is worth noting that these coatings are under compressive stress. For the composition with 50 mol.% ZrB₂, no radial cracks are observed, and pile-ups are formed around the indent. This behavior is more pronounced under a load of 350 mN, as shown in Fig. 13. Additionally, W_{pl}/W_t for this coating is 54 % (Fig. 10c). For coatings with 70 and 85 mol.% ZrB₂, only negligible cracks are detected, and these cracks are significantly shorter than those observed in the ZrB₂

coating with a columnar microstructure. Fig. 13 further illustrates that even at 85 mol.% ZrB₂, pile-ups form around the indent, consistent with a 10 % higher W_{pl}/W_t compared to the ZrB₂ coating (Fig. 10c).

For dual-phase nanocomposite Zr-Cu-B coatings deposited at 450 °C, the highest resistance to cracking is achieved for coatings with 70 and 85 mol.% ZrB₂, while the lowest resistance is seen in coatings with 50 mol.% ZrB₂ and the ZrB₂ coating. This behavior is consistent with the stress state of the coatings. Compressive stress (70 mol.% ZrB₂) inhibits crack initiation and propagation under load, whereas tensile stress (50 and 100 mol.% ZrB₂) facilitates crack opening, reducing the coating ability to resist deformation.

4. Conclusions

This work has demonstrated that the strategy applied to the ternary Zr-Cu-N system [16] can be successfully extended to the Zr-Cu-B system, enabling the design and development of dual-phase nanocomposite coatings based on nanocrystalline ZrB₂ and glassy ZrCu, even though this system exhibits a higher resistance to phase segregation. A combination of detailed experimental investigations and *ab initio* simulations provided valuable insights into the composition-dependent microstructural evolution and phase segregation mechanisms.

The findings revealed that Zr-Cu-B coatings deposited without external heating were amorphous across all compositions (50, 70, and 85 mol.% ZrB₂) investigated. Nevertheless, *ab initio* simulations indicated fingerprints of composition-dependent segregation into B-free and Cu-free zones within the amorphous structure. As the B content increased, the number of B-B bonds approached to values characteristic of an ideally segregated system.

Increasing the deposition temperature facilitated phase segregation and the formation of a dual-phase nanocomposite structure, governed by thermodynamic and kinetic factors influencing nucleation at the surface and within the coating volume. This transition was observed to depend

Fig. 12. SEM images of cube-corner indentations under 150 mN load on Zr-Cu-B coatings with different ZrB₂ molar fractions deposited without substrate heating (top row) and at 450 °C (bottom row).

Fig. 13. AFM images of cube-corner indentations under 350 mN load for Zr-Cu-B coatings prepared with 50 and 85 mol.% ZrB₂ without substrate heating.

on both the ZrB₂ content and the deposition temperature. At 50 mol.% ZrB₂, a dual-phase structure with 1–2 nm large ZrB₂ nanocrystals embedded in an amorphous matrix was achieved at 450 °C. At 70 mol.% ZrB₂, segregation initiated at 350 °C, but well-developed ZrB₂ nanocrystals (2–7 nm) with a (0001) preferred orientation surrounded by an amorphous phase were deposited at 450 °C. At 85 mol.% ZrB₂, not only ZrB₂(0001) nanocrystals nucleated on the surface, but also more randomly oriented ZrB₂ nanocrystals formed in the coating volume at temperatures as low as 250 °C. The coating grew in a columnar microstructure with an amorphous phase present predominantly at the columnar boundaries.

The mechanical properties of the Zr-Cu-B coatings reflected their compositional and structural evolution. Increasing the ZrB₂ fraction resulted in higher hardness and Young's modulus, while plastic work fraction naturally decreased. The increase in hardness and Young's modulus was also observed with increasing deposition temperature, when the amorphous structure transitioned to a dual-phase nanocomposite structure. Hardness of the dual-phase coatings increased from 12 GPa to about 22 GPa with increasing the ZrB₂ fraction. Although these values

were lower than those of binary ZrB₂ coatings, the Zr-Cu-B coatings exhibited superior plasticity and resistance to cracking, making them highly promising for applications requiring a balance of hardness, toughness, and durability.

Overall, this study has established the Zr-Cu-B system as a versatile platform for developing advanced nanocomposite coatings with tailored properties based on hard and soft phases, while highlighting their potential for future technological applications.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Deepika Thakur: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Michaela Cervená:** Validation, Methodology, Investigation. **Jirí Houška:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Software, Methodology, Investigation. **Stanislav Haviar:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation. **Tomasz Wojcik:** Investigation. **Radomír Čerstvý:** Investigation. **Alexander Kirnbauer:** Investigation. **Paul Heinz Mayrhofer:** Validation, Supervision, Resources. **Petr Zeman:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgments

This work was supported by the Czech Science Foundation under Project No. GA22-18760S and partly by the project QM4ST under Project No. CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004572 funded by Programme Johannes Amos Comenius, call Excellent Research.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

References

- [1] J. Su, C. Shi, S. Zhang, X. Dong, Y. Xu, Y. Xie, X. Lin, W. Du, High-temperature infrared emissivity stability of ZrB₂ thin Films: Influence of annealing-induced oxidation and surface passivation, *Ceram. Int.* (Jul. 2025), <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.CERAMINT.2025.07.049>.

- [2] U. Wiklund, S. Rubino, K. Kádás, N.V. Skorodumova, O. Eriksson, S. Hedberg, M. Collin, A. Olsson, K. Leifer, Experimental and theoretical studies on stainless steel transfer onto a TiN-coated cutting tool, *Acta Mater.* 59 (1) (Jan. 2011) 68–74, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actamat.2010.09.005>.
- [3] Y. Li, L. Cao, C. Qi, H. Su, Y. Wan, J. Lv, Low friction of CrN coatings in presence of glycerol, *Appl. Surf. Sci.* 514 (Jun. 2020) 145890, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apsusc.2020.145890>.
- [4] G. Zhang, B. Li, B. Jiang, F. Yan, D. Chen, Microstructure and tribological properties of TiN, TiC and Ti(C, N) thin films prepared by closed-field unbalanced magnetron sputtering ion plating, *Appl. Surf. Sci.* 255 (21) (Aug. 2009) 8788–8793, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apsusc.2009.06.090>.
- [5] E. Bousser, L. Martinu, J.E. Klemberg-Sapieha, Solid particle erosion mechanisms of protective coatings for aerospace applications, *Surf. Coatings Technol.* 257 (Oct. 2014) 165–181, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.surfcoat.2014.08.037>.
- [6] V. Moraes, L. Zauner, T. Wojcik, M. Arndt, P. Polcik, H. Riedl, P.H. Mayrhofer, Thermally stable superhard diborides: an ab initio guided case study for V-W-diboride thin films, *Acta Mater.* 186 (Mar. 2020) 487–493, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actamat.2020.01.014>.
- [7] Zhang, S. (Ed.). (2015). *Thin Films and Coatings: Toughening and Toughness Characterization* (1st ed.). CRC Press. <https://doi.org/10.1201/b18729>.
- [8] J.H. Hsieh, T.H. Yeh, S.Y. Hung, S.Y. Chang, W. Wu, C. Li, Antibacterial and tribological properties of TaN-Cu, TaN-Ag, and TaN-(Ag,Cu) nanocomposite thin films, *Mater. Res. Bull.* 47 (10) (2012) 2999–3003, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.materresbull.2012.04.101>.
- [9] R. Akhter, Z. Zhou, Z. Xie, P. Munroe, Harmonizing mechanical responses of nanostructured CrN coatings via Ni additions, *Appl. Surf. Sci.* 538 (Feb. 2021) 147987, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apsusc.2020.147987>.
- [10] J. Musil, J. Vlcek, P. Zeman, Y. Setsuhara, S. Miyake, S. Konuma, M. Kumagai, and C. Mitterer, “Morphology and microstructure of hard and superhard Zr-Cu-N nanocomposite coatings,” *Japanese J. Appl. Physics, Part 1 Regul. Pap. Short Notes Rev. Pap.*, vol. 41, no. 11, pp. 6529–6533, Nov. 2002, doi: 10.1143/JJAP.41.6529/XML.
- [11] P.J. Kelly, H. Li, P.S. Benson, K.A. Whitehead, J. Verran, R.D. Arnell, I. Iordanova, Comparison of the tribological and antimicrobial properties of CrN/Ag, ZrN/Ag, TiN/Ag, and TiN/Cu nanocomposite coatings, *Surf. Coatings Technol.* 205 (5) (Nov. 2010) 1606–1610, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.surfcoat.2010.07.029>.
- [12] W. Gulbiński, T. Suszko, Thin films of Mo₂N/Ag nanocomposite—the structure, mechanical and tribological properties, *Surf. Coatings Technol.* 201 (3–4) (Oct. 2006) 1469–1476, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.surfcoat.2006.02.017>.
- [13] R. Akhter, A. Bendavid, P. Munroe, Effect of Ni content on the microstructure and mechanical properties of TiN coatings, *Appl. Surf. Sci.* 573 (Jan. 2022) 151536, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apsusc.2021.151536>.
- [14] J. Musil, M. Zitek, K. Fajfrlik, and R. Čerstvý, “Flexible antibacterial Zr-Cu-N thin films resistant to cracking,” *J. Vac. Sci. Technol. A Vacuum, Surfaces, Film.*, vol. 34, no. 2, 2016, doi: 10.1116/1.4937727.
- [15] R. Daniel, T. Ziegelwanger, M. Zitek, M. Červená, S. Haviar, M. Meindlhummer, P. Baroch, J. Keckes, P. Zeman, Multilayer design of sustainable multifunctional Zr-Cu-N coatings: a route for enhanced mechanical and antibacterial performance, *Mater. Des.* 254 (Jun. 2025) 114037, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matdes.2025.114037>.
- [16] P. Zeman, S. Haviar, J. Houska, D. Thakur, A. Bondarev, M. Červená, R. Medlín, R. Čerstvý, Self-formation of dual-phase nanocomposite Zr-Cu-N coatings based on nanocrystalline ZrN and glassy ZrCu, *Mater. Des.* 245 (Sep. 2024) 113278, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matdes.2024.113278>.
- [17] M. Stüber, H. Riedl, T. Wojcik, S. Ulrich, H. Leiste, P.H. Mayrhofer, Microstructure of Al-containing magnetron sputtered TiB₂ thin films, *Thin Solid Films* 688 (Oct. 2019) 137361, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tsf.2019.06.011>.
- [18] M. Zhang, G. Yang, L. Zhang, Y. Zhang, J. Yin, X. Ma, J. Wen, L. Dai, X. Wang, H. Chen, L. Zhang, L. Yin, X. Jian, X. Zhao, L. Deng, Application of ZrB₂ thin film as a low emissivity film at high temperature, *Appl. Surf. Sci.* 527 (Oct. 2020) 146763, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apsusc.2020.146763>.
- [19] X. Gu, C. Liu, H. Guo, K. Zhang, C. Chen, Sorting transition-metal diborides: New descriptor for mechanical properties, *Acta Mater.* 207 (Apr. 2021) 116685, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actamat.2021.116685>.
- [20] H. Li, L. Zhang, Q. Zeng, J. Wang, L. Cheng, H. Ren, K. Guan, Crystal structure and elastic properties of ZrB compared with ZrB₂: a first-principles study, *Comput. Mater. Sci.* 49 (4) (Oct. 2010) 814–819, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.commatsci.2010.06.027>.
- [21] V. Moraes, h. Riedl, C. Fuger, P. Polcik, H. Bolvardi, D. Holec, and P. H. Mayrhofer, “Ab initio inspired design of ternary boride thin films,” *Sci. Reports* 2018 81, vol. 8, no. 1, pp. 1–9, Jun. 2018, doi: 10.1038/s41598-018-27426-w.
- [22] Y. Wu, J. Pan, X. Fan, Q. Lu, Y. Gong, X. Huang, K. Chang, T. Wang, J. He, Magnetron sputtering method for the preparation of Cu-ZrB₂ composite film and their optical properties, *J. Alloys Compd.* 983 (May 2024) 173850, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jallcom.2024.173850>.
- [23] M. Zhang, M. Li, Z. Yan, L. Zhang, J. Yin, X. Ma, W. Li, L. Deng, Multifunctional Ag-ZrB₂ composite film with low infrared emissivity, low visible light reflectance and hydrophobicity, *Appl. Surf. Sci.* 604 (Dec. 2022) 154626, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apsusc.2022.154626>.
- [24] T. Fiantok, M. Truchlý, V. Šroba, T. Roch, V. Izai, M. Vidiš, M. Haršáni, L. Satrapinský, and M. Mikula, “First Approach to ZrB₂ Thin Films Alloyed with Silver Prepared by Magnetron Co-Sputtering,” *Coatings* 2023, Vol. 13, Page 663, vol. 13, no. 3, p. 663, Mar. 2023, doi: 10.3390/coatings13030663.
- [25] B. Wicher, O.V. Pshyk, X. Li, V. Rogoz, I. Petrov, L. Hultman, G. Greczynski, Superhard oxidation-resistant Ti_{1-x}Al_xB₂ thin films grown by hybrid HiPIMS/DCMS co-sputtering diboride targets without external substrate heating, *Mater. Des.* 238 (Feb. 2024) 112727, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matdes.2024.112727>.
- [26] J. Chrzanowska-Giżyńska, P. Denis, M. Giżyński, L. Kurpaska, I. Mihailescu, C. Ristoscu, Z. Szymański, T. Mościcki, Thin WB_x and W_xTi_{1-x}B_x films deposited by combined magnetron sputtering and pulsed laser deposition technique, *Appl. Surf. Sci.* 478 (Jun. 2019) 505–513, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apsusc.2019.02.006>.
- [27] “CPMD 3.13.1, IBM Corp. 1990-2008, MPI Fur Festkorperforschung Stuttgart, 1997-2001, Wwww.cpmdd.org.”.
- [28] N. Marks, Evidence for subpicosecond thermal spikes in the formation of tetrahedral amorphous carbon, *Phys. Rev. B - Condens. Matter Mater. Phys.* 56 (5) (1997) 2441–2446, <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevB.56.2441>.
- [29] J. Houska, S. Kos, Ab initio modeling of complex amorphous transition-metal-based ceramics, *J. Phys. Condens. Matter* 23 (2) (Jan. 2011) 025502, <https://doi.org/10.1088/0953-8984/23/2/025502>.
- [30] J. Houska, J. Kohout, J. Vlcek, Effect of N and Zr content on structure, electronic structure and properties of ZrBCN materials: an ab-initio study, *Thin Solid Films* 542 (Sep. 2013) 225–231, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tsf.2013.07.010>.
- [31] L. Tengdelius, M. Samuelsson, J. Jensen, J. Lu, L. Hultman, U. Forsberg, E. Janzén, H. Högborg, Direct current magnetron sputtered ZrB₂ thin films on 4H-SiC(0001) and Si(100), *Thin Solid Films* 550 (Jan. 2014) 285–290, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tsf.2013.11.040>.
- [32] C. Mitterer, J. Komenda-Stallmaier, P. Losbichler, Sputter deposition of decorative boride coatings, *Vacuum—volume 46* (11) (1995) 1281.
- [33] P. Zeman, M. Zitek, Zuzjaková, and R. Čerstvý, “Amorphous Zr-Cu thin-film alloys with metallic glass behavior,” *J. Alloys Compd.*, vol. 696, pp. 1298–1306, 2017, doi: 10.1016/j.jallcom.2016.12.098.
- [34] J. Houska, P. Machanova, M. Zitek, P. Zeman, Molecular dynamics and experimental study of the growth, structure and properties of Zr-Cu films, *J. Alloys Compd.* 828 (Jul. 2020) 154433, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jallcom.2020.154433>.
- [35] S. Mahieu, P. Ghekiere, D. Depla, R. De Gryse, Biaxial alignment in sputter deposited thin films, *Thin Solid Films* 515 (4) (2006) 1229–1249, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tsf.2006.06.027>.
- [36] J.A. Thornton, High rate thick film growth, *Annu. Rev. Mater. Sci.* 7 (1977) 239–260, <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.ms.07.080177.001323>.
- [37] Z. Chen, L. Hao, C. Li, Q. Gao, J. Xu, J. He, Z. Yuan, D. Yu, Surface properties and work function of ZrB₂ single crystal, *Phys. Lett. A* 513 (Jul. 2024) 129606, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.physleta.2024.129606>.
- [38] T.Y. Tsui, G.M. Pharr, W.C. Oliver, C.S. Bhatia, R.L. White, S. Anders, A. Anders, I. G. Brown, Nanoindentation and nanoscratching of hard carbon coatings for magnetic disks, *MRS Proc.* 383 (1995) 447, <https://doi.org/10.1557/PROC-383-447>.
- [39] M. Apreutesei, P. Steyer, L. Joly-Pottuz, A. Billard, J. Qiao, S. Cardinal, F. Sanchette, J.M. Pelletier, C. Esnouf, Microstructural, thermal and mechanical behavior of co-sputtered binary Zr-Cu thin film metallic glasses, *Thin Solid Films* 561 (2014) 53–59, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tsf.2013.05.177>.